

BIOINSPIRED HIERARCHICAL FUNCTIONAL MATERIALS TEMPLATED FROM NATURAL STRUCTURES

D. Zhang^{1*}, W. Zhang¹, J.J. Gu¹, S.M. Zhu¹, H.L. Su¹, Q.L. Liu¹, T.X. Fan¹, C.L. Feng¹

¹ State key lab of metal matrix composites, Shanghai Jiao Tong University, 800 Dong Chuan Road, Shanghai, 200240 China

* Corresponding author (zhangdi@sjtu.edu.cn)

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1 General Introduction

Scientists are always amazed by the biological materials, which are characterized by unique structures and morphologies. Inspired by nature, scientists struggle to fabricate artificial structures with certain functions in a biomimetic way. There has been a great interest in using biomaterials with subtle hierarchical structures as biotemplates to fabricate biomorphic inorganic materials. In recent years, different biotemplating technologies have been developed for the conversion of biological templates into biomorphic ceramics.

In this review, the latest developments in this field will be discussed. The review is organized into three parts. In the first part, versatile inorganic materials using different wood issues as templates will be discussed. The second part will give an overview on the butterfly wings microstructure materials. The last part deals with investigations on the bacteria transforms by various analytical techniques. Finally, we will give the summary, expectation and our own perspectives on these active areas.

2 Functional materials fabrication inspired from nature materials

2.1 Inspired from wood

As a group of the plant, wood is a heterogeneous, hygroscopic, cellular and anisotropic material, composed of fibers of cellulose and hemicellulose held together by lignin. Wood exhibits microstructural features ranging from mm (growth ring patterns) via μm (tracheidal cell patterns, macro- and microfibril cell wall textures) down to nm scale (molecular cellulose fibers and membrane structures of cell walls). Since all the cell walls in the wood link together to form a frame, the body of the wood is then divided into innumerable rooms by this frame. After being heated in high temperature, the mixed biopolymers in the cell walls decomposed

into carbon and gases. This gives rise to a porous carbon frame with the morphology derived from its wood template. Our work convinced that the porous carbon wood microstructure has many favorable characteristics such as stable coefficient of friction, good electromagnetic shielding properties, excellent far infrared property and high damping capacity. These outstanding properties of the wood can be attributed to its rational structures.

Fig. 1: SEM images of microstructures of TiC wood ceramics converted from wood species: (a) larch, (b) franxinus mandshurica, (c) black walnut, and (d) lauan. (e)–(h) are SEM images showing corresponding microstructure of original wood tissues of: (e) larch, (f) franxinus mandshurica, (g) black walnut, and (h) lauan.

2.2 Inspired from agricultural wastes

An agricultural establishment produces many types of wastes in its daily operations. Agricultural waste materials particularly those containing cellulose shows potential metal bio-sorption capacity. The basic components of the agricultural waste materials biomass include hemi-cellulose, lignin, extractives, lipids, proteins, simple sugars etc., which is very similar to the wood tissues. To loose the environment pressure and increase the economic value of these wastes, re-using them is a very urgent topic. Studies reveal that various agricultural waste materials such as rice husk, coconut shells, vegetable residues etc. have great potential in electromagnetic

wave absorption applications. Here some research details are given in the full review.

2.3 Inspired from butterfly wings

In butterfly wings, the colorization mechanisms can be divided into two categories: pigment color and structural color. The former category is determined by the color of the pigments or dyes, which are common in the wings. In comparison, structural color comes from the hierarchical structures in the wing scales. The brilliant colors generated from the scales' complex architectures at the sub-micrometer level attracted interests from scientists in biology, physics and materials science.

Very recently, wing scales of natural Lepidopterans (butterflies and moths) manifested themselves in providing excellent three dimensional (3D) hierarchical structures for surface-enhanced Raman scattering (SERS) detection. But the origin of the observed enormous Raman enhancement of the analytes on 3D metallic replicas (shown in Fig.2) of butterfly wing scales has not been clarified yet, hindering a full utilization of this huge natural wealth with more than 175 000 3D morphologies. Herein, the 3D sub-micrometer Cu structures replicated from butterfly wing scales are successfully tuned by modifying the Cu deposition time. An optimized Cu plating process (10 min in Cu deposition) yields replicas with the best conformal morphologies of original wing scales and in turn the best SERS performance.

Fig. 1: SEM element mapping images of seven metallic wing-scale replicas.

The work introduced in the above section all used different butterfly wings directly as bio-templates. Due to the limitation of the direct templating methods, such as template selecting, uniform batch production and large scale usage, several biomimetic fabrication processes were developed to address these limitations. More details will be in the full paper of this review.

3 Conclusion

As described in this review, significant developments have been made in morph-genetic materials using nature materials as templates during the last years. The field continues to grow internationally and contribute to new interdisciplinary areas concerned with the synthesis, self-assembly and processing of organized matter across arrange of length scales. Morph-genetic materials, as the result of learning from nature, will change our life styles and bring us to a higher level of civilization. The fabrication method may be applied to other nature substrate template and inorganic systems that could eventually lead to the production of optical, magnetic. or electric devices or components as building blocks for nanoelectronic, magnetic, or photonic integrated systems

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